

TEACHER'S TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND CONSTRUCTIVIST APPROACH ON LEARNING MOTIVATION OF LEARNERS: A MODERATION ANALYSIS

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Teacher's Technological Pedagogical Knowledge and Constructivist Approach on Learning Motivation of Learners: A Moderation Analysis

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Abstract

The current study was set evaluate whether teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge have significant moderating effect on the interaction between constructivist approach and learning motivation of learners. In this study, the researcher selected the 196 public elementary school teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental as the respondents of the study. Stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. Non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected on the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Heirarchical Regression Analysis. Descriptive analysis showed that teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge and learning motivation of learners were described as extensive, while, teachers' constructivist approach was rated as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there is significant relationship among teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge, constructivist approach, and learning motivation of learners. Evidently, heirarchical regression analysis proved that teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge have significant moderating effect on the interaction between teachers' constructivist approach and learning motivation of learners. In other words, teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge is a significant moderator on the interaction between constructivist approach and learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

Keywords: *educational management, teachers' pedagogical strategies, self-directedness among learners, parental support*

Introduction

Motivating the learner to learn is pertinent to curriculum implementation. This is because motivation is an influential factor in the teaching-learning situations. The success of learning depends on whether or not the learners are motivated. Motivation drives learners in reaching learning goals. It is important to recognize the fact that motivating learning is a central element of good teaching. This implies that learners' motivation is probably the single most important element of learning. For teachers, a lack of motivation has long been one of the most frustrating obstacles to learners' learning. Teachers are the key factor in motivating students to engage in learning activities within their specific educational contexts. It is important to note that motivation, which is a psychological construct, is also a teaching technique that could be used to enhance learning motivation in the classroom.

Meanwhile, highlighted that getting learners to learn and sustaining their interest in what they are learning remains an unresolved issues among teachers worldwide (Filgona et al., 2020). As a fact, Carnegie Mellon University (2019) argue that the reasons why learners are less motivated when learning are that they do not believe their efforts will improve their performance and that they have other priorities more preoccupying their attention. Dişlen (2013) also argued, learners are less motivated and have poor academic performance due to boring lessons and complex tasks without a detailed explanation from the lecturer. More so, Wright (2017) also states that feeling of being unable to do the given tasks, less confident in learning and having deficient relationship or communication with lecturers also cause students to have low motivation.

Similarly, in a survey with 3,000 school-aged students across the United Kingdom, Elevate Education (2020) found that learner's motivation levels plummeted during the national school closures from March to July 2020 up to the present with 81% of the surveyed students stating that they felt unmotivated to learn during those months. As suggested by decades of psychological research, motivation is developmentally interlocked with academic achievement throughout an individual's education. Simamora (2020) also reported that the learners claimed that they are not motivated to attend classes because it caused them some health problems like fatigue, headache, or fever because they had too many assignments to do in short time. Some also declared that they had impairment eyesight due to long duration starring at computers or phones screens. These disadvantages which determined the learners' success in learning were closely related to learners' motivation in the classroom after the two years of being subjected to pandemic learning mode.

In contrary, Firman and Rahayu (2020) remote learning set-up was reported beneficial for students because they become motivated due to high interaction to rich learning materials regardless time and place as well as high opportunity to experience digital learning programs. Moreover, the Pakpahan and Fitriani (2020) noted that high interaction also occurred in the forms of virtual communication among teachers- students, and students - students which resulted vast capacity of sharing information and experience. As the online teaching and learning processes used computer technology, it increased enthusiasm of both teachers and students to participate which, in turn, increased their computer skills too.

On one hand, Yıldırım (2014) defined teacher's constructivist classroom management approach as a student-centered environment where learners generally support each other's learning and construct knowledge by using information resources and various tools to

solve a problem or to reach their learning goals. In such a classroom, Tunca (2015) described that teachers provide experience with the knowledge constructing process, which means making the learners gain experiences on how to construct knowledge.

On the other hand, Hosseini and Kamal (2012) defined technological pedagogical knowledge as the knowledge of technology tools that can enhance learning and teaching. According to Baran et al. (2011) technological pedagogical knowledge is a clear understanding on how preservice teachers can effectively apply technology in their teaching approach and practices. Koehler et al. (2012) also stated that technological pedagogical knowledge is about having the knowledge of how to improve teaching and learning processes when technologies are being fully utilized. In some cases, Alayyar et al. (2012) mentioned that technological pedagogical knowledge can also address how pedagogies change while using ICT.

Moreover, previous studies indicated significant relationship among technological pedagogical knowledge, constructivist classroom management approach and learning motivation of the learners. However, most of them were conducted in foreign setting. As an example, Cetin-Dindar (2016) found that constructivist classroom management approach enhances students' motivation towards learning by consisting of student-centered approaches. Accordingly, constructivist learning environment enhances learners to interact with knowledge and each other using various tools and emphasizes on the learning environment where learning occurs rather than instruction itself. Also, Jorde and Dillon (2012) noted that in a constructivist learning environment, the teacher is to act as a facilitator and guides learners to achieve learning goals. Moreover, Phillips (2014) argued that teachers should possess a deeper, more essential understanding and mastery of information technology for information processing, communication, and problem solving. Accordingly, teachers with a deeper understanding of technology knowledge effectively apply technology in their work and personal lives through the recognition of when technology could assist or hinder the achievement of a goal.

In short, it can be concluded that various factors largely influence learners' poor learning motivation. These factors originate from within the learners themselves and outside the environment. However, in this study, the researchers wanted to discover whether technological pedagogical knowledge moderates the relationship between teachers' constructivist approach and learning motivation of the learners. This study would fill-up the gap since it made use of quantitative descriptive-correlational design utilizing hierarchical regression analysis. More so, the author selected the learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao oriental for this research because the researcher is also a teacher in one of these schools under this district.

Research Questions

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate the moderating effect of teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge on the interaction of constructivist approach on learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge (moderating variable)?
2. What is the extent of the teacher's constructivist approach to the learners in terms of:
 - 2.1. communication and interaction;
 - 2.2. relation establishment;
 - 2.3. skills development;
 - 2.4. time usage and assessment; and
 - 2.5. learning and teaching?
3. What is the extent of learning motivation of the learners in terms of:
 - 3.1. self-efficacy;
 - 3.2. learning strategies;
 - 3.3. performance goals; and
 - 3.4. learning environment simulation?
4. Is there significant relationship among teacher's technological pedagogical knowledge, constructivist approach, and learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental?
5. Do technological pedagogical knowledge have significant moderating effect on the interaction of constructivist approach on learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a non-experimental design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique of research, which is designed to gather data, ideas, facts and information related to the study. Quantitative research deals in numbers, logic and objective stance. It focuses on numeric and unchanging data and detailed, convergent reasoning, generation of a variety of ideas about a research problem (Babbie et al. 2010). According to Myers and Well (2013) correlated design examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause and effect relationship between variables. It enabled the researcher to observe two variables at a point in time and was useful in describing the relationship of the factors of both variables. Moreover, the study also looked into the relationship among three variables– technological pedagogical knowledge, constructivist approach, and learning motivation of the learners. The

interest of the study is to investigate whether technological pedagogical knowledge moderates the interaction of constructivist approach on learning motivation in terms of self-efficacy, learning values, performance goals, and learning environment simulation. Thus, the study only focused on the behavioral aspect other factors that came up in the conduct of the study were not considered.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the elementary school teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. In this study, the 196 respondents was selected through stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information.

In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular elementary school teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental, and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions and thus it did not consider the socio-economic status and gender of the teachers.

Instruments

The study employed the questionnaires that was a researcher-made and modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into three parts. The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before the administration of the instrument, it was subject for validation of three experts, and was revised according to their expert comments.

The first part is about the teacher's constructivist approach in Cluster 4 schools in Davao City which was adopted from the study of Yildirim (2014) indicated with communication and interaction, relation establishment, skills development, time usage and assessment, and learning and teaching. The Cronbach coefficient value for this instrument is 0.946 described as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. More so, this questionnaire was subjected for content validity by panel of experts to test its validity. As a guide in determining the extent of teacher's constructivist approach, the researcher made use of the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below:

<i>Range of Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	Teacher's constructivist approach is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	Teacher's constructivist approach is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teacher's constructivist approach is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	Teacher's constructivist approach is seldom observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	Teacher's constructivist approach is never observed.

The second part of the instrument concerned about the learning motivation of the learners. This questionnaire was adopted from the study of Tuan et al. (2005) measured in terms of self-efficacy, learning values, performance goals, and learning environment simulation. The reliability of the original scale was obtained a Chronbach's alpha value of 0.930. More so, this questionnaire was subjected for content validity by panel of experts to test its validity. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of learning motivation, the researcher made use of the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below.

<i>Range of Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	Learning motivation is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	Learning motivation is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Learning motivation is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	Learning motivation is seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	Learning motivation is never manifested.

The third part of the instrument concerned about the teacher's technological pedagogical knowledge. This questionnaire was adapted from the study of Hosseini and Kamal (2012). The reliability of the original scale was obtained a Chronbach's alpha value of 0.955. More so, this questionnaire was subjected for content validity by panel of experts to test its validity. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of teacher's technological pedagogical knowledge, the researcher made use of the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below.

<i>Range of Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	Teacher's technological pedagogical knowledge is always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	Teacher's technological pedagogical knowledge is oftentimes evident.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teacher's technological pedagogical knowledge is sometimes evident.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	Teacher's technological pedagogical knowledge is seldom evident.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	Teacher's technological pedagogical knowledge is never evident.

Procedure

Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire.

Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public elementary schools in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

To obtain the permission to conduct the study from the selected public elementary schools in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental, the letters were personally brought by the researchers to the principals of the schools where the study was conducted. The researcher initially appeared in the office of the principals last February 2023 to carry the letters asking the permission to conduct the study. The letters were accepted by the principals. However, the principals reminded the researcher that during the conduct of the study, the protocols that were set by the Division Superintendent should be strictly followed. This includes the no disruption of classes as well as the health protocols in relation to the COVID-19 crisis. After which, the researcher proceeded to the distribution and retrieval of the survey questionnaires.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey was briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After which, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis.

Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, the scores of each respondents was tallied to organized the data per indicator. After which, each score were subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS

Data Analysis

The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data:

Mean. This was useful in determining the extents of teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge, constructivist approach, and learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. Mean and standard deviation are descriptive statistics that tend to measure how the score clustered and scattered, respectively. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1, 2, and 3.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was utilized to determine the significance of the relationship among the three variables- teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge, constructivist approach, and learning motivation of learners. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r .

Hierarchical Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the moderating effect teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge on the interaction of constructivist approach and learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher observed promptly the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessments criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study.

Informed Consent. The researcher asked for the permission of respondents through a written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study and ample explanations were given to them for better understanding of the reason for their participation so that they can choose whether to participate or not.

It was made clear that respondents involvement in the study is voluntary. If ever they would refuse to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious to assure the respondents' psychological well-being. A written permission from the respondents were secured from them. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote the learning motivation of learners in relation to teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge and constructivist approach, and may contribute to the enhancement.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. The respondents of the study are teachers so they are not considered vulnerable since all of

them are in legal age, and, they are not considered highly vulnerable in the psychological aspect. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed.

Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the data Privacy Act of 2012 wherein the researcher assured that the data cannot be traced back to the participants which were the real source of information, to protect the identities of the participants. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the respondents. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, the access was limited to the researcher alone. To protect the privacy of the participants, it was assured that the researcher is the only person that could access the survey results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the survey result to assure that data cannot be traced back to the respondents who were the real source of information.

Risk, Benefits and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study as well as the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the survey questionnaire. The respondents, without restrictions were able to asked questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not be subjected to harm in any ways whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire that were used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents of the study.

Likewise, this study is designed purely to collect academic information related to the study and they were not asked with personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher made sure that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents were given freedom not to answer questions which made them feel any psychological and emotional distress and they would be free to withdraw as a respondent of the study if they would feel that they cannot discuss the information that being asked from them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the course of the study.

Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equal regardless if they would be respondent in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the respondents of the study. Anybody who fitted the qualifications of being permanent-regular in the purposively selected schools. During the conduct of the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting as little time as possible to the routine of the respondents. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenir. The tokens were sent via courier, and these were sealed carefully in a package. Also, each tokens were sanitized before having it sent to your doorstep.

Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any type of communication in relation to the research was done with honesty and transparency. To safeguard the welfare of the respondents, the researcher properly implemented the methods that are discussed to use in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis was included. Importantly, the researcher described the extent of the involvement of the respondents in this study and shared how the researcher maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presentation of the results of the study.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that the responses of the respondents were not influenced by any other factor like the conflict of interest. The findings of the study could be accessed by the respondents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the study, the Division of Davao Oriental was given a furnished copy of the results of the research so it can be accessed by the respondents and be used for learning and further study.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials which were ample and available in the conduct of the study and was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding properly the ratings of the respondents during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results gathered were proficient and aligned that serves as a primary basis for adequacy.

Community Involvement. It was a good practice to have community involvement during every phase of research, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement would be accorded with primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate method to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge, constructivist approach, and learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental; the significant relationship among variables; and the moderating effect of technological pedagogical knowledge on the interaction between teachers' constructivist approach and learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

Teachers' Technological Pedagogical Knowledge in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental

Consequently, teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental as shown on Table 1 is described as extensive with a category mean of 3.40. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.99 to 3.68. The item, Thinking critically about how to use technology in the classrooms reflects a mean rating of 2.99, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as item sometimes evident in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. Further, the item Using technology for more collaboration and communication with students has a mean rating of 3.68, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

The result implies that the knowledge of technology tools that can enhance learning and teaching is oftentimes evident among respondents in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This finding supports the proposition of Baran et al. (2011) that technological pedagogical knowledge is a clear understanding on how teachers can effectively apply technology in their teaching approach. Therefore, technological pedagogical knowledge is about having the knowledge of how to improve teaching and learning processes when technologies are being fully utilized. Likewise, the result agrees with Shaukenova's (2016) assertion that knowledge of teachers on how to use computers and other ICT related devices improves positive attitude of the students towards computers because it help organize the students by helping them to gain thoughtful understanding and to familiarize themselves with several educational resource.

Table 1. *Extent of Teachers' Technological Pedagogical Knowledge in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1.	Choosing technology that can enhance the teaching approaches for a lesson.	3.66	Extensive
2.	Choosing technology that enhances students' learning for a lesson.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
3.	Thinking critically about how to use technology in the classrooms.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
4.	Adapting the use of the technologies that I am learning about to different teaching activities.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
5.	Using technology tools and information resources to increase productivity.	3.41	Extensive
6.	The teacher can fuse technology to strategies of teaching.	3.45	Extensive
7.	Using technology for more collaboration and communication with students.	3.68	Extensive
8.	Knowing how to use technology to facilitate learning.	3.47	Extensive
	Mean	3.40	Extensive

Communication and Interaction. In terms of communication and interaction, Table 2 shows a moderate extensive category mean rating of 3.12 which means that this domain of teachers' constructivist approach is sometimes observed by the teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.99 to 3.53. The item, Having significant influence over what happens in my school reflects a mean rating of 2.99, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes observed. Meanwhile, the item, Having a great deal of control over what happens in my school shows a rating of 3.53, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed among teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

Table 2. *Extent of Teacher's Constructivist Approach in Terms of Communication and Interaction*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1.	Taking learner opinions into account.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
2.	Encourage me to take the floor, to speak and to to discuss to express their opinions.	3.09	Moderately Extensive
3.	Encouraging me to be enterprising.	3.06	Moderately Extensive
4.	Encouraging me to make decisions independently.	2.95	Moderately Extensive
5.	Encouraging me to communicate both with me and each other.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
6.	Supporting the development of the feeling of responsibility in the learners.	3.01	Moderately Extensive
7.	Including the learners in rule making and decision making process.	3.08	Moderately Extensive
8.	Supporting the development of self-discipline skills in the learners.	3.54	Extensive
	Mean	3.12	Extensive

The result denoted that the reciprocal actions that take place in a room, in a school, between the teacher and the learners is sometimes observed by the teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This result is similar to Mohammed's (2012) view that in the constructivist classroom setting, the students are urged to be actively involved in their own process of learning. In the constructivist learning environment, both teacher and students think of knowledge as a dynamic, ever-changing view of the world we live in and the ability to successfully stretch and explore that view - not as inert factoids to be memorized.

Relation Establishment. Table 3 shows that constructivist approach in terms of relation establishment got a moderately extensive category mean rating of 3.33 which means that this domain of teachers' constructivist approach is sometimes observed in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.09 to 3.47. The item, Asking open-ended questions which provoke thinking in the learners reflects a mean rating of 3.09, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes observed. Meanwhile, the item, Stimulating the prior knowledge and previous experiences of learners in order to facilitate the construction of knowledge shows a rating of 3.47, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed among teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

The result emphasizes that teachers were sometimes able to give learners the opportunity to establish relationship between what they learn and the facts and concepts in nature. They give feedback in order to supplement the learning acquired in the class. This result is consistent to the findings of Yliportimo (2016) constructivist learning environment teaching offers the learners the opportunity to acquire skills and knowledge through first hand experiences, reflect upon those experiences and transform it to functional experiences in daily life situations.

Table 3. *Extent of Teacher's Constructivist Approach in Terms of Relation Establishment*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1.	Giving feedback to learner.	3.44	Extensive
2.	Giving learners the opportunity to establish a relationship between what they learn and the facts and concepts in nature.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
3.	Asking open-ended questions which provoke thinking in the learners.	3.09	Moderately Extensive
4.	Guiding the learners to give meaning to what they learn.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
5.	Stimulating the prior knowledge and previous experiences of learners in order to facilitate the the construction of knowledge.	3.47	Extensive
	Mean	3.33	Moderately Extensive

Skill Development. The result on Table 4 shows that the domain, skills development, was assessed by the teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental as extensive with a category mean of 3.53, interpreted as oftentimes observed. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.23 to 3.74. It is noteworthy that item, Supporting the development of information access and the usage skills of the learners has a mean rating of 3.23, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes observed while item, Supporting the development of question asking, the questioning and research skills has a mean rating of 3.74, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed by respondents in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

This means that the process wherein they use cognitive skills or strategies that increase the probability of a desirable learning outcome in constructivist learning environment is oftentimes observed among respondents in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This finding supports Alsaleh's (2020) proposition that those students who can regulate their learning are able to evaluate the outcomes of their thought processes, calculate how good a decision is, or identify how effectively a problem has been solved. Likewise, it also supports the view of Panadero (2017) that development of skills can be stimulated by adjusting learning environments to self-regulated learning which can be done by implementing one or more educational interventions that are believed to self-regulate learning. In addition, Bramucci (2013) noted that learners' self-regulated learning strategies that they employ were found to be predictive of their performance on standardized tests.

Table 4. *Extent of Teacher's Constructivist Approach in Terms of Skill Development*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1.	Supporting the development of question asking, the questioning and research skills.	3.74	Extensive
2.	Supporting the development of high level thinking skills of the learners.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
3.	Supporting the development of the problem solving skills of the learners.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
4.	Supporting the development of information access and the usage skills of the learners.	3.23	Moderately Extensive
5.	Supporting the development of purpose determination and the realization skills of the learners.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
	Mean	3.36	Moderately Extensive

Time Usage and Assessment. In terms of impact, Table 5 shows a moderate extensive category mean rating of 3.29 which means that this domain of teachers' constructivist approach is sometimes observed in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.13 to 3.63. The item, Giving the learners enough time in learning activities reflects a mean rating of 3.13, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes observed. Meanwhile, the item, Encouraging the learners to make self-assessment shows a rating of 3.63, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed among teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

This means that learners sometimes organized their schedule in such a way that they achieve their goals efficiently and effectively. This finding is parallel to the view of Obijiaku (2015) that for the learners, managing time is an important area of their self-desire to achieve or reach their academic goals and can be challenging for most of them if they do not know exactly how to go about it.

According to Clark (2014) having the accurate awareness of time usage can help to monitor one's self at all times and also to keep track of unnecessary activities which does not need attention. Thus, activity planning can help the learners actualize their aims and work towards them and it can also make them avoid some irregular habits which can be distract them.

Table 5. *Extent of Teacher's Constructivist Approach in Terms of Time Usage and Assessment*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1.	Giving the students the necessary time for answering the questions.	3.36	Moderately
2.	Giving the learners enough time in learning activities.	3.13	Extensive
3.	Encouraging learners to use the time efficiently and effectively.	3.26	Moderately

4.	Using different assessment techniques to evaluate the learners.	3.15	Extensive
5.	Taking the learning process of the students into consideration, rather than the results in the assessment.	3.24	Moderately
6.	Encouraging the learners to make self-assessments.	3.63	Extensive
	Mean	3.29	Moderately

Learning and Teaching. Specifically, examining the domain of learning and teaching, results on Table 6 reveal that its category mean is 3.42 described as extensive which means that this particular domain on teachers' constructivist approach is oftentimes observed in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.15 to 3.66.

It is noteworthy that item, Using various teaching methods and techniques which are consistent with the lesson's purpose has a mean rating of 3.15, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes observed while item, Centering learning around learners' interests and needs has a mean rating of 3.66, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed.

Table 6. *Extent of Teacher's Constructivist Approach in Terms of Learning and Teaching*

	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1.	Conducting the lesson by focusing on principal concepts.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
2.	Using various teaching methods and techniques which are consistent with the lesson's purpose	3.15	Moderately Extensive
3.	Devising some activities in the lesson to attract learner attention and to increase participation.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
4.	Devising learning activities for the active learning of the learners.	3.60	Extensive
5.	Centering learning around learners' interests and needs.	3.66	Extensive
	Mean	3.42	Extensive

This implies that teachers use various teaching methods and techniques which are consistent with the lesson's purpose is oftentimes observed among teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This finding is in agreement with the view of Temli- Dumus (2016) that the effective utilization of instructional management is another technique of effective classroom management adopted by teachers in the classroom.

Learning Environment Organization. In terms of learning environment organization, Table 7 shows an extensive category mean rating of 3.31 which means that this domain of teachers' constructivist approach is sometimes observed in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.15 to 3.54. The item, Using various real materials and primary sources for supporting the participation reflects a mean rating of 3.15, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes observed. Meanwhile, the item, Presenting real life problems or unsolved incidents to the students shows a rating of 3.54, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes observed among teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

Table 7. *Extent of Teacher's Constructivist Instructional Approach in Terms of Learning Environment Organization*

	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1.	Presenting real-life problems or unsolved incidents to the students.	3.54	Extensive
2.	Making learning possible outside of the school as well as in it.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
3.	Using various real materials and primary sources for supporting the participation	3.15	Moderately Extensive
4.	Preparing an order of seating which facilitates the communication and interaction among the learners.	3.29	Moderately Extensive
	Mean	3.31	Moderately

This means that the teachers' oftentimes show the ability to cooperatively manage space, resources, and students' roles and behaviors, so as to provide a climate that encourages learning. This finding supports the notion of Savas and Gurel (2014) noted that teachers who were able to organized learning environment effectively was able to manage their classroom better and positively affect student achievement and behaviors.

Lastly, Table 8 shows the summary on the extent of teachers' constructivist approach in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. As shown in the table, teachers' constructivist approach obtained an overall mean score 3.29, descriptively rated as moderately extensive, interpreted as sometimes observed. The result denotes that teachers were able to set of skills that creates a student-centered environment where learners generally support each other's learning and construct knowledge by using information resources and various tools to solve a problem or to reach their learning goals.

The finding supports the view of Tunca (2015) that in such a classroom, teachers provide experience with the knowledge constructing process, which means making the learners gain experiences on how to construct knowledge. Also, Anagün (2018) pointed out that since this is a classroom setting which are technology-based in which learners are engaged in meaningful interactions, students could able to hypothesize, predict, manipulate objects, pose questions, research, investigate, imagine, and invent.

Table 8. *Summary Table on the Extent of Teachers' Constructivist Approach in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Communication and Interaction	3.12	Moderately Extensive
Relation Establishment	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Skills Development	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Time Usage and Assessment	3.29	Moderately Extensive
Learning and Teaching	3.42	Extensive
Learning Environment Organizations	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.29	Moderately Extensive

Learning Motivation of Learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental

Self-Efficacy. Learning motivation in terms of self-efficacy as shown in Table 9 has a category mean of 3.48, described as extensive and interpreted as this particular domain of learning motivation is oftentimes manifested among the respondents in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.21 to 3.65. Specifically, the item, Finding the lessons easy and understandable, shows a mean rating of 3.21, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. The item, Doing well in tests reflects a mean rating of 3.65 described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

This implies that the belief in one's ability to perform well in class learning tasks is oftentimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This finding is congruent to Aurah's (2017) assertion that when a learners is confident in his own ability or behave in such a way, the learner can make a difference in how he feels, thinks and acts, such as in science related learning or activities. Adding more, the result is also congruent to Ozmentes' (2014) claim that learners who perceive their performances to be more adequate than it actually is tend to be more successful in their performances.

Table 9. *Extent of Learning Motivation of Learners in Terms of Self-Efficacy*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Finding the lessons easy and understandable.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
2. Doing well in tests.	3.65	Extensive
3. Being able to answer activities by myself.	3.58	Extensive
Mean	3.48	Extensive

Active Learning Activities. This particular domain of learning motivation, learning value, as shown in Table 10 reflects an extensive category mean of 3.53 which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.08 to 3.74. The table further reveals that the item Trying to find out why when I make a mistake in class activities has a mean rating of 3.08, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Finding relevant resources (such as books, journals, internet sources, etc.) that will help me when I do not understand a concept reflects a mean rating of 3.74, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested by the teachers in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

The result implies that the use of variety of strategies to construct new knowledge based on their previous understanding is oftentimes manifested among the learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. The findings agrees with the view of Kubischta (2014) that effective learners are self-regulating, analyzing task requirements, setting productive goals, and selecting, adapting or inventing strategies to achieve their objectives. These learners also monitor progress as they work through the task, managing intrusive emotions and waning motivation as well as adjusting strategies processed to foster success.

Table 10. *Extent of Learning Motivation of Learners in Terms of Active Learning Activities*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1. Connecting my previous knowledge to the new topic during class.	3.68	Extensive
2. Discussing with the teacher or other students to clarify my understanding when I do not understand a concept.	3.63	Extensive
3. Trying to find out why when I make a mistake in class activities.	3.08	Moderately Extensive
4. Finding relevant resources (such as books, journals, internet sources, etc.) that will help me when I do not understand a concept.	3.74	Extensive
Mean	3.53	Extensive

Learning Value. Consequently, learning motivation in terms of learning value as shown on Table 11 is described as extensive with a category mean of 3.56. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.28 to 3.77. The item, Thinking learning is important because it helps me learn to solve problems reflects a mean rating of 3.28, described as moderately extensive, and interpreted as item sometimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. Further, the item Thinking learning is important because it stimulates thinking has a mean rating of 3.77, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested. It suggests that the acquisition of problem-solving efficiency, mastery the investigation prosperity, shake their own taking into consideration, and find the pertinence of

humanities with daily life is oftentimes manifested among the learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This finding supports the proposition of Altındağ and Senemoğlu (2013) that when people acquired these skills, it allows students to be aware of what an individual knows and does not know, thus, developing their abilities to apply appropriate motivated strategies for learning basic livelihood skills.

Table 11. *Extent of Learning Motivation of Learners in Terms of Learning Value*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1.	Thinking learning is important because it is useful in my daily life.	3.50	Extensive
2.	Thinking learning is important because it stimulates thinking.	3.77	Extensive
3.	Thinking learning is important because it helps me learn to solve problems.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
4.	Class gives me the opportunity to answer questions in my mind.	3.69	Extensive
	Mean	3.56	Extensive

Performance Goal. This particular domain of academic motivation, performance goal, as shown in Table 12 reflects an extensive category mean of 3.33 which means that it is sometimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.97 to 3.52. The table further reveals that the item Participating in the class activities not to compete with my classmate but to learn together and to share ideas has a mean rating of 2.97, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Participating in the class activities not only to get good grades but also to learn new things reflects a mean rating of 3.52, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

The result denotes that the goals in learning of the learners to compete with other students and to get attention from the teacher is sometimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This finding agrees with the view of Guido and Dela Cruz (2011) concluded that effective teaching strategies influence learner's learning motivation. Adding more, the result also agrees with Akomolafe and Adesua (2015) that through an effective teaching strategy, the learners were able to know how to plan and implement the strategies of solution to the question and problems.

Table 12. *Extent of Learning Motivation of Learners in Terms of Performance Goal*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1.	Participating in the class activities not only to get good grades but also to learn new things.	3.52	Extensive
2.	Participating in the class activities not to compete with my classmate but to learn together and to share ideas.	2.97	Moderately Extensive
3.	Participating in the class activities not to impress my teacher but to fulfill my curiosity.	3.51	Extensive
	Mean	3.33	Moderately Extensive

Learning Environment. This particular domain of learning motivation, learning environment, as shown in Table 13 reflects an extensive category mean of 3.37 which means that it is sometimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.09 to 3.60. The table further reveals that the item Being willing to participate in the class because the topics is exciting and challenging has a mean rating of 3.09, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Being willing to participate in the class because I am given the opportunity to express my idea reflects a mean rating of 3.60, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

The result denotes that the learning environment surrounding students, such as curriculum, teachers' teaching, and pupil interaction influence learners' academic motivation is sometimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This finding agrees with the view of Cetin-Dindar (2016) that constructivist learning environment enhances learners' motivation towards learning by consisting of student-centered approaches. Accordingly, constructivist learning environment enhances learners to interact with knowledge and each other using various tools and emphasizes on the learning environment where learning occurs rather than instruction itself.

Table 13. *Extent of Learning Motivation of Learners in Terms of Learning Environment*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1.	Being willing to participate in the class because the topics is exciting and challenging	3.09	Extensive
2.	Being willing to participate in the class because I am given the opportunity to express my idea.	3.60	Moderately Extensive
3.	Being interested in participating in the class activities because the teacher gives me enough time to complete the task.	3.47	Extensive
	Mean	3.37	Moderately Extensive

Lastly as shown in the Table 14 is the summary on the extent of learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. As shown in the table, the overall mean of learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental is 3.46 which is described as extensive. Also, the table indicates that learning motivation in terms of learning value acquired the highest mean score of 3.56 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while, learning motivation in terms of performance goal acquired the lowest mean score of 3.33 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested.

The result means that the internal condition that stimulates, directs and maintains an attitude of learning is oftentimes manifested in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This finding supports the view of Guido (2013) that learners who are highly motivated to learn express effort in attaining a goal, show persistence, attend to the tasks that are necessary to achieve the goals, have a strong desire to attain their goal, enjoy the activities necessary to achieve their goal, are aroused in seeking their goals, have expectancy about their successes and failures.

Table 14. *Summary Table on the Extent of Learning Motivation of Learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Self-Efficacy	3.48	Extensive
Active Learning Activities	3.53	Extensive
Learning Value	3.56	Extensive
Performance Goal	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Learning Environment	3.37	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.46	Extensive

Adding more, the study also agrees with the view of Chumbley et al. (2015) that highly motivated students are more betrothed in acquisition and they do practical tasks more completely than the ones with low motivation. According to Albalate, Larcia and Jaen (2018), learners who are highly motivated to learn are efficient in using cognitive and metacognitive strategies. Likewise, Hubert (2017) noted that highly motivated learners can control various mental strategies for better cognitive performance, enhanced ability to attend to things in a selective and focused way, can concentrate over a period of time, easily learn new information and skills, can determine strategies for actions, easily comprehend scientific language and can retain information and manipulate it to solve complex scientific problems.

Significant Relationship among Teachers' Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Constructivist Approach and Learning Motivation of Learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental

The results on the analysis on the relationship between constructivist approach, learning motivation of learners, and teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 15 shows that teachers' constructivist approach has a significant positive relationship with the learning motivation of learners with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .731, p < .05$). It means that as the extent of the teachers' constructivist approach changes, learning motivation of learners also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers' constructivist approach and learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. The findings agrees with the proposition of Basheer (2014) that people learn best by trying to make sense of something on their own, with the teacher as a guide to help them along the way. Also, this agree with Fox and Schirmmacher (2012) that the word facilitator is more appropriate than teacher in social constructivist context where the learner is actively constructing knowledge, rather than passively taking in information.

Table 15. *Significant Relationship among Teachers' Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Constructivist Approach and Learning Motivation of Learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Learning Motivation</i>	<i>Technological Pedagogical Knowledge</i>
Constructivist Approach	0.225**	0.468**
	0.000	0.000
Learning Motivation	1	0.334**
		0.000

**Significant at $p < 0.05$

On one hand, the result shows that the relationship between teachers' constructivist approach and technological pedagogical knowledge in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental has a significant positive relationship with a p-value of .00 that is less than alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.675, p < 0.05$). This means that if the extent of teachers' constructivist approach changes, the extent of technological pedagogical knowledge in Cateel 2 District in Davao Oriental also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between between teachers' constructivist approach and technological pedagogical knowledge in Cateel 2 District in Davao Oriental. The finding is in agreement with Ozerem and Akkoyunlu (2015) that in a classroom aligned in constructivist learning environment principle, knowledge is developed through cognitive activity which happens through the discussion of experiences with other individuals or in groups.

On the other hand, the result shows that the relationship between teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge has a significant positive relationship with the learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District in Davao Oriental with a p-value of .00 that is less than alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.681, p < 0.05$). This means that if the extent of teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge changes, learning motivation of learners also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge has a significant positive relationship with the learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. The finding is parallel to the findings of Samarkandi (2012) that the ability of the teachers to assist and

encourage students to use computer technology and multimedia software to learn and retrieve information helps to keep the students engaged in learning; it appeals to their needs to be stimulated through their multiple senses, and it allows them to increase their confidence with computer-based technology that transcends all components of their didactic and clinical learning.

Moderating Effect of Technological Pedagogical Knowledge on the Interaction Between Teachers' Constructivist Approach and Learning Motivation of Learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental

The moderating effect of teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) on the relationship between constructivist approach (CA) and learning motivation (LM) of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental were tested using hierarchical regression analysis. Results on the Table 16 shows that the Beta coefficients for the Step 1 analysis of teachers' constructivist approach (CA) and learning motivation (LM) of learners were $\beta = 0.106$, S.E. = 0.056, $p < 0.05$; and teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) and learning motivation (LM) of learners were $\beta = 0.212$, S.E. = 0.049, $p < 0.05$. When teachers' constructivist approach (CA) and technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) were included as the only independent variables (without including an interaction term), the regression model explained 64.50% of the variance in learning motivation (LM) of learners ($R^2 = 0.645$, $p < .05$).

Table 16. Moderating Effect of Teachers' Technological, Pedagogical Knowledge on the Interaction Between Constructivist Approach and Learning Motivation of Learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental

	Step 1	Learning Motivation (LM)				
		B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decisions
Constructivist Approach (CA)		.106**	.131	.056	.000	Reject H ₀
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)		.212**	.078	.049	.000	Reject H ₀
R ²	= 0.645	F-value = 118.604**			p-value = 0.000	
Step 2						
Constructivist Approach (CA)		.382**	.576	.031	.000	Reject H ₀
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)		.179**	.126	.048	.000	Reject H ₀
Moderator (CA*TPK)		.221**	.089	.052	.000	Reject H ₀
R ²	= 0.776	F-value = 139.099**			p-value = 0.000	

**Significant at $p < 0.05$

Moreover, Beta coefficients for the Step 2 analysis of teachers' constructivist approach (CA) and learning motivation (LM) of learners were $\beta = 0.382$, S.E. = .031, $p < 0.05$; teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) and learning motivation (LM) of learners were $\beta = 0.179$, S.E. = 0.048, $p < 0.05$; and moderator (CA*TPK) and learning motivation (LM) of learners were $\beta = 0.221$, S.E. = 0.052, $p < 0.05$. Also, it was indicated that when an interaction between teachers' constructivist approach (CA) and technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) was added, the percentage of variance in learning motivation (LM) of learners was 77.60% ($R^2 = 0.776$; $p < 0.05$) indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 13.10% of variance in the dependent variable ($\Delta R^2 = 0.131$). Based on the result, the null hypothesis was rejected as teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) had significantly moderated the relationship between constructivist approach (CA) and learning motivation (LM) of learners.

The finding is parallel to the view of Cetin-Dindar (2016) that constructivist learning environment enhances learners to interact with knowledge and each other using various tools and emphasizes on the learning environment where learning occurs rather than instruction itself. In a constructivist learning environment, the teacher is to act as a facilitator and guide learners to achieve learning goals. Through constructivist teaching approaches, learners freely voice their own thoughts and share their opinions.

Adding more, the result is in agreement with Milner et al. (2012) claims that motivation is sustained through real world issues and projects. In a constructivist learning environment, students are encouraged thoughtful reflection on experience, learn to analyze real world issues, learn how to investigate, develop their collaboratively learning and inquiry skills, build communication skills, improve their learning strategies skills, and reach a collective outcome over a period of time. Lastly, the result supports Knolton's (2014) TPACK framework which describes the interaction of knowledge about how to teach, what to teach, and how to do so with the use of ICT. Accordingly, in-service teachers are becoming more creative when exposed in a technology-enhanced learning environment.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions (such as survey questionnaire and number of participants), several conclusions are generated:

Teachers' technology pedagogical knowledge in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental was extensive. The result denotes that teachers were able to set of skills that creates a student-centered environment where learners generally support each other's learning and construct knowledge by using information resources and various tools to solve a problem or to reach their learning goals.

Teachers' constructivist approach in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental was extensive. Teachers' constructivist approach in terms of

communication and interaction, relation establishment, skills development, time usage and assessment, and learning environment acquired a moderately extensive rating, while teachers' constructivist approach in terms of learning and teaching acquired an extensive rating. The result denotes that teachers were able to set of skills that creates a student-centered environment where learners generally support each other's learning and construct knowledge by using information resources and various tools to solve a problem or to reach their learning goals.

Learning motivation of the learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental was extensive. Learning motivation of learners in terms of self-efficacy, active learning activities, and learning value acquired extensive rating. It means that the internal condition that stimulates, directs and maintains an attitude of learning is oftentimes manifested.

Teachers' constructivist approach has a significant positive relationship with the learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. On one hand, teachers' constructivist approach has a significant positive relationship with the technological pedagogical knowledge in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. On the other hand, teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge has a significant positive relationship with the learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

Teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge have significant moderating effect on the interaction between constructivist approach and learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental. This affirmed that teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge is an undeniable factor that strengthened the interaction between constructivist approach and learning motivation of learners in Cateel 2 District, Davao Oriental.

The researcher recommends that school administrators should put to consideration on giving a great importance like changing the room's physical layout may make the classroom a more attractive place for learning. Through increasing the attractiveness of classroom environment, it reduces stress within the classroom and facilitate learning because the room should be arranged to ensure that all students can see well, there are no obstructions, the lighting is adequate, and when students move around, they do not interfere with other students, resulting to increases in desire for knowledge and heightens creativity among students.

More so, the researcher recommends that the teachers should draw on professional relationships and learners' families for continued guidance and support in finding ways to address the academic motivation of individual learners and consider parents, school personnel, and behavioral experts as allies who can provide new insights, strategies, and support. Further, it is also recommended that school administrators should provide time and structures for collaborative learning teams to meet. Effective teams are relatively small, interdisciplinary groups comprised of grade-level general education teachers and—when needed—administrators, special educators, or other specialists that meet weekly or bi-weekly. An action-oriented agenda and facilitation by team leaders who skillfully guide the discussions without assuming an authoritative role promote productive meetings.

Lastly, researchers should conduct further analysis on the factor that may contribute to the interaction between constructivist approach and learning motivation (LM) of learners since it was found that when the interaction between teachers' constructivist approach (CA) and teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) was added, the percentage of variance in learning motivation (LM) of learners was only 77.60%.

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